
Chronic Obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), unveiling Pathophysiology, Genomics, Advancement in Diagnosis and therapeutic strategies: A brief review

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Conflict of interest: None

ABSTRACT

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) stands as a formidable challenge in global healthcare, demanding a comprehensive understanding of its pathophysiology, genomic underpinnings, and advancements in diagnostics and therapeutics. The pathophysiology of COPD unfolds as a complex interplay of chronic bronchitis and emphysema, characterized by persistent airflow limitation. This narrative unties the molecular intricacies, emphasizing the role of inflammatory cascades, oxidative stress, and protease-antiprotease imbalances in driving disease progression. Genomic investigations illuminate COPD's heterogeneity, revealing genetic susceptibilities and highlighting the interplay with environmental factors. Advancements in COPD diagnosis underscore a paradigm shift towards precision medicine. From traditional spirometry to cutting-edge imaging and biomarker analyses, a nuanced approach emerges, allowing for early detection and personalized intervention. Genomic markers serve as sentinel guides, heralding a new era in tailored therapeutic strategies. Therapeutic strides in COPD management showcase innovations ranging from bronchodilators to anti-inflammatory agents. Novel interventions targeting specific molecular pathways bring optimism, promising improved outcomes and enhanced quality of life for patients. As we traverse the COPD landscape, this exploration integrates science communication with clinical relevance, fostering an interdisciplinary dialogue crucial for shaping the future of COPD research and patient care.

Key words: COPD, Pathophysiology, Genomics, therapeutic strategies

INTRODUCTION

Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease COPD involves a group of diseases that cause difficulty breathing and prevention of smooth airflow in the lungs. COPD is a progressive and multifactorial disease that cannot be reversed completely. Emphysema and chronic bronchitis are the two most common diseases that progress toward COPD and can vary from mild to severe. COPD has been the third most common cause of death in 2019, resulting in 3.2 million demises, the highest mortality rate (almost 80%) in developing and underdeveloped countries (1). COPD mortality rates have seen an inclined shift from 44.5 million in 1990 to 75.1 million in 2010 in South-East Asian countries (2). Studies have shown that COPD is directly linked with increased economic burden by putting pressure on substantial costs of healthcare facilities. In the year 2010 in the United States, COPD had a direct cost of 32 billion dollars whereas indirectly it caused a loss of 20.4 billion dollars through other reasons like lost working hours (3). COPD is a multifactorial disease, influenced by both environmental

and genetic factors. Smoking is considered to be the number one cause of chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. 9 out of 10 cases of COPD exist due to smoking (4).

The harmful toxins present in cigarette smoke can disrupt the airway linings present in the lungs, studies have also indicated that passive smoking can also be a cause of COPD in nonsmokers. Similarly, air pollution is another risk factor in the development of COPD in individuals exposed to it. Polluted air contains isocyanates, silica dust, cadmium fumes, coal dust, and welding fumes (5). Other common risk factors for COPD include underdeveloped lungs, history of respiratory infections including asthma, consumption of tobacco, family history of lung diseases, as well as occupational exposure to inhaled carcinogens (6). Exposure to these pollutants can influence the functioning of your respiratory tract and can put an individual at risk of having COPD.

PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF COPD

Swelling of bronchial tube linings is observed in chronic bronchitis which carries air to and from the air sacs present in the lungs and ultimately results in the production of mucus and coughing. Whereas in emphysema the air sacs at the end of bronchioles get damaged because of exposure to certain inhaled pollutants and toxins. Symptoms of Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease including tiredness, difficulty breathing or breathlessness, and lasting cough start appearing as soon as the patient hits middle age. People having COPD are often seen having other medical conditions like muscular and skeletal disorders, cardiovascular diseases, anxiety, depression, and sometimes lung cancer.

GENETIC ASSOCIATIONS OF COPD (CAUSATIVE FACTORS)

Alpha 1 antitrypsin (AAT)

SERPINA1 gene encodes Alpha 1 antitrypsin, which belongs to the superfamily of serpine protease inhibitors. Synthesized in the liver, AAT acts as a major inhibitor to a serine protease enzyme called neutrophil elastase. In addition to that, AAT also inhibits many other proteinases including caspase-3, matrilysin, kallikreins, and ADAM-17 enzymes. In 1964, AAT deficiency was reported for the very first time in two patients having emphysema with a severe breathing disorder. AAT is an antiprotease that balances the activity

of neutrophil elastase (7). This depicts that inherited deficiency of AAT is associated with development of emphysema during early years of life and also that genetic factors can play a significant role in antiprotease balance in the body.

Protease and Antiprotease imbalances in COPD

Proteases are enzymes that digest elastin which is responsible for lung elasticity and many other structural proteins of the lungs whereas antiproteases protect against these proteases. An imbalance between these two is directly linked with respiratory disorders. It also induces the release of inflammatory factor (IL-8) from epithelial cells and thus controls inflammation of cells in the lung parenchyma. Proteinase 3 and cathepsin G released by macrophages also have similar roles. Alpha 1 antitrypsin deficiency is involved in causing COPD. This gene is involved in the protection of your lungs. AAT is a protein synthesized in your liver that helps protect your lungs from any damage. People having mutations or deficiency of this gene is a rare genetic disorder and leads to the development of emphysema and if not treated, causes COPD. An individual may have AAT deficiency in conditions for example if he has a family history of having emphysema, liver disease, bronchiectasis, swelling of fat cells beneath the layers of skin, or he develops emphysema during the early stage of his life before 45 years, even after developing emphysema without being exposed to any possible risk factors like cigarette smoke or continued exposure to air pollutants and toxic fumes (8).

Inflammatory Cells

COPD can be caused by either Chronic Obstructive Bronchiolitis which is swelling or ultimately fibrosis of peripheral airways in the lungs or the loss of elastic capability (occurring mainly because of some destructive activity in the parenchyma of lungs) leading to emphysema.

In patients with COPD, there is an increased amount of neutrophils in Bronchoalveolar Lavage fluid. Biopsy examinations have shown the presence of T lymphocytes as well as neutrophils in the peripheral airways which obstruct airways. Biopsy samples of ex-smokers also show the same kind of airway obstruction. The presence of such neutrophils in air passageways causes the release of enzymes like metalloproteinases (MMP) and neutrophil elastase which add to the pathophysiology of COPD. Similarly, macrophages

are also involved in causing inflammation of the lungs in patients with COPD by releasing proteolytic enzymes and chemotactic factors. An increased concentration of macrophages has been observed in the BAL fluid of COPD patients. Increased proteolytic activity in the lungs of COPD patients is also directly linked with the presence of macrophages (9). These macrophages along with neutrophils and epithelial cells produce metalloproteinase enzymes that are endopeptidases and are involved in the degradation of extracellular lung components including collagen, laminin, elastin, fibronectin, and proteoglycans. Patients having emphysema are recorded with increased metalloproteinases (MMP1 and MMP9) which directly highlights the involvement of macrophages in COPD.

Oxidative stress and COPD

Patients having COPD are observed with elevated levels of oxidative stress because of oxidants in cigarette smoke and also exogenously generated ROS. Many enzymes are engaged in generating ROS and many antioxidants are present that diminish or balance the effect of these reactive oxygen species in the lungs.

Detoxifying enzymes

Genetic alterations of the enzymes involved in the detoxification of harmful substances present in cigarette smoke or other inhaled toxins can also directly account for the development of COPD. Cigarette smoke produces harmful epoxide intermediates which are metabolized by an enzyme called microsomal epoxide hydrolase. Patients having COPD and emphysema are found to have slow metabolizing variants of this enzyme (10). Similarly, a gene called

CYP1A1 encoding cytochrome P450 is involved in metabolizing the conversion of hydrocarbons in smoke to carcinogens. Mutations in this gene are linked with increased activity of the enzyme and rapid conversion of those polyaromatic hydrocarbons into cancer-causing agents and thus are involved in elevated risk of emphysema and lung cancer (11).

Cytokine genes

Cytokines are also said to be involved in the inflammatory mechanism in COPD. TNF- α is present in the sputum of COPD patients in abundance. This protein enhances the inflammation process by amplifying the expression of genes responsible for causing inflammation, for example, IL-8. On the contrary, another cytokine IL-10 induces anti-inflammatory effects by reducing the expression of IL-8, TNF- α , certain MMPs, and other chemokines whereas induces the expression of metalloproteinases tissue inhibitors and also increases apoptosis of neutrophils. People exposed to cigarette smoke and other inhaled irritants experience reduced secretion of IL-10 from macrophages and thus have more inflammatory cytokines than normal (12).

Role of viruses and bacteria in COPD

Studies have shown that bacterial and viral infections also play a role in COPD exacerbations. During diagnosis, almost 78 percent of COPD cases have these infections, out of which 23.3% were viral, 29.7% bacterial and the rest of them were co-infections (13). Data has shown that viral and bacterial infections were involved in increasing the severity of the disease. Moreover, variations in the microbiome of the lungs are interrelated with events of COPD exacerbations and cause the mediation of inflammatory responses in the host. Similarly many conditions like bronchiectasis can affect the complexity and composition of lung microbiota and thus influence the severity of exacerbations in patients with COPD.

MANAGEMENT AND TREATMENT OF COPD

The goal is to manage the causative agents and modulate responses in the body of the host. COPD can be treated through a blend of different approaches for example targeting inflammation, targeting bacterial and viral infection in the lungs, targeting respiratory failure, preventing the recurrence of early exacerbations, and prevention of exacerbations through the management of chronic diseases.

Treating lung inflammation & Targeting infections

Corticosteroids: Corticosteroid therapy is known to reduce the failure of treatment and is associated with improvements in patients having lung disorders. It can also reduce the period of a patient's stay at the hospital. But literature gives us evidence of its negative impacts, for example, its long-term exposure can lead to osteoporotic fracture, venous thrombosis, and sepsis. Every 1 in 6 COPD patients treated with steroids develop hyperglycemia. Moreover, it is also associated with a high risk of pneumonia and an increased mortality rate (14).

Antibiotics: About 86% of hospitalized COPD patients are prescribed antibiotics. But not all patients have bacterial infections so to limit antibiotic resistance in patients with COPD, its dosage should be monitored (15).

Antivirals: Patients with COPD most commonly have Rhinovirus, the influenza virus has also been detected in COPD cases. In general, coronavirus has also been associated with the early onset of COPD, and such patients can have severe outcomes because of the presence of (SARS-COV-2). Antiviral treatments include a calculated dosage of remdesivir and dexamethasone. Modulating interferons is another way to treat viral infections (16). However, trials are still going on to investigate the advantages of interferons in patients with COPD exacerbations.

Bronchodilators : Patients with COPD are being treated with bronchodilators i.e methylxanthines are being given intravenously but their use is limited nowadays because of their toxicity profiles and side effects (17).

Controlled oxygen therapy: This treatment is also beneficial but hyperoxia can lead to adverse conditions like respiratory acidosis and increased death rates. Optimized saturation levels of 88% to 92% should be maintained during targeted oxygen therapies (18).

RECENT ADVANCEMENTS IN TREATMENT OF COPD

Recent advances for the treatment of COPD include bronchodilator therapies such as long acting androgenic receptor agonists (LABAs) and long acting muscarinic receptor antagonists (LAMAs), which can result in reduced breathlessness, increased lung function and decreased exacerbations (19). However, their use during the initial stage treatment of COPD is still under debate.

Biological therapy

In this case, several antibodies are made such as against interleukin IL-5, and monoclonal antibodies are established for the treatment of eosinophilic asthma and to prevent COPD exacerbations (20). Similarly, mepolizumab is a biological drug known to eosinophils in blood and sputum production in COPD patients. Benralizumab acts similarly.

Statins

Statins are of huge interest in the treatment of COPD because they are known for their anti-inflammatory effects as well as their influences on cardiovascular diseases. They are also known to reduce exacerbations in COPD patients (21).

Mucolytics

Mucolytics are also involved in lowering exacerbations in COPD patients. In addition to that, they also have anti-inflammatory effects and antioxidant effects. Studies have indicated that higher dosages of mucolytics in mild COPD have reduced the rate of exacerbations by approximately 19.4% (22).

Vaccinations

Patients with COPD are advised to get pneumococcal and influenza vaccinations. It reduces the rate of community-acquired influenza and pneumonia (23). A study has shown that proper vaccinations cause a 27% decreased rate of hospitalization in COPD patients as well as reduced exacerbations.

DISCUSSION

In previous years, the continuous search for drugs except for bronchodilators for the treatment of COPD patients including nitric oxide synthase, IL-1 β , TNF- α , β -2 integrin, IL-13, I κ B kinase (inhibitor of nuclear factor kappa B), adenosine receptor 2 α , and phospholipase A2 have enabled us to study and discover the therapeutic potential of novel molecules having pharmacological potential. With improvements in COPD management, certain drugs have been proved effective in clinical trials performed using animal models while some of them have shown hazardous side effects along with their therapeutic properties, limiting their use. Genetic associations with COPD have demonstrated various genetic influences contributing towards the progression of the disease. Several genes including MMP12, SERPINA1, FAM13A, HHIP, TGF- β 1, and EPHX1 have been linked with COPD susceptibility (24). Still, genetic studies have certain limitations for instance varying behavior smoking patterns, exposure to pollutants, comorbidities and overall behavioral effects. Critical clinical COPD manifestations including complex phenotypes, impacts of respiratory infections on exacerbations, as well as systemic COPD manifestations still need to be understood completely. Various COPD complexities may arise from the combined influence of disease related genes coupled with inflammatory disorders, microbial infections affecting lungs, as well as other processes including hemorrhage, thrombosis or fibrosis, triggering immune responses and associated apoptosis/necrosis (25). Certain therapeutic approaches for example restoring the function of α 1 antitrypsin or the use of antioxidants that are Nrf-2 dependent can directly block and inhibit the processes involved in disease severity including pro-apoptotic mediators' activation and proteolysis of extracellular matrix (26, 27). A common challenge that exists is to restore the survival mechanisms of lung without catalyzing the process of ontogenesis. Moreover, recent studies aimed at the regeneration of lungs in COPD mouse models, puts strain on the fact that extent of macromolecular destruction in lungs imposed by years of lung injury needs to be determined while selecting best possible treatment approaches (28). Different proteases involved in generating immuno-inflammatory responses are responsible for the destruction of elastin fibers in parenchyma of lungs, contributing to the development of emphysema leading to COPD. Therefore, the identification of those inflammatory cytokines and understanding their interactive pathways is crucial for the success of anti-inflammatory treatment strategies for COPD (29).

CONCLUSION

It is estimated that the burden of COPD will continue to increase in the coming years because of continued exposure to the risk factors of COPD including smoking, increased air pollution index, and many others. Understanding the economic burden COPD has put specially on patients, society and healthcare workers is important to establish approved therapeutic and early diagnostic strategies for better management of the disease. With increased severity, it is difficult to manage patient's symptoms as well as exacerbations. COPD affects the health of patients severely and leads to more than 75% loss of lung function as the disease progresses. It also results in weakness of peripheral muscles, breathing problems, a decrease in outdoor activities, and fitness loss. People have worsening life quality with frequent exacerbations and there is always a mortal risk. Current treatments and therapies for COPD are broad and we should move across a standardized approach. Biomarkers need to be established and clinical trials need to be done to prevent and treat COPD. Specific pathways involved in the disease need to be targeted through novel drugs to reduce its rate in the future.

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